

Communicative Competence, Occupational Self-efficacy, and Job Satisfaction in Secondary English Teachers of Kolkata with Special Reference to Competency over English Language

Atrayee Saha

Psychologist, St. Judes High School, Hyderabad, Telangana

Communicative Competence is the expertise that speakers and listeners apply in different social contexts to communicate appropriately (Dell Hymes, 1972). Occupational self-efficacy refers to one's belief in one's expertise to excel in work-related tasks or activities (Felfe & Schyns, 2006). Job satisfaction refers to that positive emotional state which one feels when one's job experiences are appraised (Schneider & Snyder, 1975). English for Speakers of Other Languages in short represent ESOL. ESOL classes are designed mainly for those English speakers who are not native by nature and for whom English is their third or fourth language to develop language and comprehension skills. Correlational design is adopted to determine if there is any relation between communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction in English teachers. Between group design is adopted for determining gender differences with respect to competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. For selecting sample, a non-probability purposive sampling method was used. During the data collection, 50 English teachers were obtained out of which 25 are males and 25 are females. The findings showed communication competence and occupational self-efficacy share positive relation and positive relation between communicative competence and job satisfaction in English teachers. The findings showed differences in gender with respect to communicative competence where females score is higher than males and job satisfaction where males score is higher than females. The findings suggest that gaining competence over communication specially over English language through proper soft skills training is imperative for every working professional as that would enhance their self-efficacy levels with respect to their occupational lives and they would feel satisfied with their jobs.

Keywords: Communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, job satisfaction, between group design

In today's world, gaining competence over communication has become imperative besides scoring good marks in academics. It has become one of the determining factors for personnel selection in different job sectors which in turn enhances one's level of self-efficacy with respect to occupational life. This, in turn, brings satisfaction in one's job life. In this context, competency in English speaking skills poses an extra challenge for white collar workers seeking jobs in different sectors since English has emerged as a slightly more demanding language as compared to other languages and this expectation is comparatively higher for those who have pursued English in their higher studies. Hence, gaining competence over English speaking skills has become little more demanding for English teachers teaching in English medium schools as this would enhance their occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction level.

Communicative Competence is the expertise that speakers and listeners apply in different social contexts to communicate appropriately (Hymes, 1972).

Elements of communicative competence are: (Hymes, 1982:22)

- Participants including both senders and receivers.

- Participants sharing available channels code.
- Every setting.
- Every form of message, topic, and events themselves.

Communicative Competence has some components:

Grammatical Competence: It deals with mastery of language code. It comprises certain abilities like coding linguistic, recognizing description of language related to lexical, morphology, syntax, and phonology over which mastery is gained followed by manipulating these features to produce words and sentences (Canale, 1983: 7).

Sociolinguistic Competence: It implies understanding of the context when a language is used socially. Some factors in this context play important role like participants status sharing of information, interaction purposes, and interaction norms or conventions (Savignon, 1983:37).

Discourse Competence: Here, meaningful whole is formed and unity of text is achieved by interpreting a series of sentences and utterances (Savignon, 1983:38).

Strategic Competence: It refers to gaining competence over strategies related to verbal and non-verbal communication for compensating communication break down which occurs due to limiting conditions in actual communication which in turn enhances communication effectiveness (Tarone & Cohen, 1983).

Occupational self-efficacy refers to one's belief in one's expertise to excel in work-related tasks or activities (Felfe & Schyns, 2006).

Features of occupational self-efficacy (Wallin et al., 2021):

Belief in One's Competence: It refers to a person's belief in their abilities to meet requirements and demands of their jobs.

Author Note

Atrayee Saha, Psychologist, St. Judes High School, Hyderabad Telangana

I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Atrayee Saha, Psychologist, St. Judes High School, Hyderabad Telangana

E-mail: atrayee25091998@gmail.com

Specificity with Respect to Task and Behavior: It deals with specific tasks (e.g., completing technical work) or broader occupational behaviors, such as career decision-making or seeking new job opportunities.

Personal Resources: It refers to one's psychological resources like coping and adjustment skill, self-efficacy level, resilience which one implements at workplace to overcome challenges and meet various demands of workplace and adapting oneself to workplace changes.

Positive Impact on Work Outcomes: Occupational self-efficacy shares positive relation with higher job motivation, better work ability, and increased engagement.

Factors determining occupational self-efficacy (Wallin et al., 2021):

Work Ability and Engagement: Higher occupational self-efficacy shares positive relation with better overall work ability and higher work engagement.

Personalized Goal: Building followed by achieving realistic and attainable goals enhances stronger sense of self-efficacy in the workplace.

Feedback and Support: Receiving value for goal attainment constructive feedback with respect to strengths and limitations from employers would enhance one's self-efficacy in the workplace.

Growth Mindset: Perceiving challenges in the workplace as learning opportunities fosters confidence and self-efficacy of a person in their workplace.

Job satisfaction refers to that positive emotional state which one feels when one's job experiences are appraised (Schneider & Snyder, 1975).

The following are the components of job satisfaction (Ćulibrk et al., 2018):

Affective: It refers to the response that one shows emotionally towards one's own job.

Cognitive: One's own perception with respect to how one's job could fulfil one's requirements.

Behavioral: It refers to the act that one exhibits upon evaluating one's level of job satisfaction. This may result in more productivity or more absenteeism from employees side.

Job satisfaction has the following determinants (Ćulibrk et al., 2018):

Nature of Job: Challenging, meaningful, and interesting job enhances job satisfaction among employees.

Pay and Rewards: Adequate salary, recognition, and other perks from organization are essential for job satisfaction among employees.

Career Growth: Opportunities involving more advancement in career life are essential for job satisfaction.

Supervision: Cooperative, friendly, supportive, competent supervision from employer's side enhance one's job satisfaction level.

Work Environment: Safe and pleasant physical environment along with positive social environment enhance one's level of job satisfaction.

Co-workers: Maintaining friendly, supportive, and positive relation with co-workers enhances job satisfaction among employees.

Fair Policies in Workplace: Implementing fair policies in workplace by employers enhance sense of trust and satisfaction in employees.

Job satisfaction has following consequences (Ćulibrk et al., 2018):

- Positive consequences in case of satisfaction:
 - Productivity among employees is increased.
 - Absenteeism is reduced among employees.
 - Commitment level among employees is increased.
 - Organizational behavior gets enhanced in employees.
- Negative consequences in case of dissatisfaction:
 - Turnover level among employees increases where employees intent to leave the job.
 - Performance level gets reduced in employees due to decreased effort and increased error rate.
 - Deviant behavior is increased which involves neglect behavior, chronic absenteeism, and lateness among employees.

Teachers play important roles in bringing improvement in certain domains of students' lives like gaining abilities and expertise in academics, maturity over emotions, moral character, and spirituality. Thus, teachers competency plays an important role in bringing success in students learning abilities. Teachers competency includes gaining competency over certain components like pedagogy, personality, and social domains, and through professional education attaining Sinval and Marôco (2020) professional competence (Harden & Crosby, 2000).

If teachers mainly English teachers are not gaining mastery over English speaking skills, how would they pass on that skill to students since teachers serve as role models to students. Hence, teachers mainly English teachers should gain competency in communication skills to help students gain mastery over English language acquisition skills (Caena & Redecker, 2019).

In this context, the concept of ESOL plays extremely important role specially for whom English is third or fourth language. English for Speakers of Other Languages in short represent ESOL. ESOL classes are designed mainly for those English speakers who are not native by nature and for whom English is their third or fourth language to develop language and comprehension skills. Its implementation is different from what we normally see in day to day teaching methods, especially for those students who are well versed in English while growing up.

Teachers are given responsibilities to make students proficient in English besides doing other tasks, so students can meet grade-level content requirements. Some ESOL classes are conducted separately to make students proficient in English and then they get an allowance to join mainstream classes upon gaining competency over English. On the other hand, some ESOL classes are included in mainstream classes beforehand (Fradd & Lee, 1998).

Review of Literature

A study conducted by Usman et al. (2016) which focused to explore the influence of competence of teachers towards students motivation in learning English showed that teachers' competence in English which is coming under one of their cognitive abilities motivates students to learn English as a subject.

In addition to the above study, another study was conducted by Belasoto (2021) to explore the impact of competency on communication in English teachers of colleges to use its results a basis for an action plan, highlighted some of the important factors that enhances communicative competence. These factors are- the practice of the English language inside and outside the classroom,

exposure to mainstream media, as English teachers gain experience, intelligence is inherited, and attending seminars or trainings. Some factors like time, attitude or preference of the teacher, environment, teaching load, co-workers and students are perceived to influence the exposure of the above factors.

Again in another study conducted by Chamani., Safaeizadeh, and Xodabande (2023) which focused to investigate relation between occupational self-efficacy, satisfaction, meaning at work and their subjective well-being in 120 EFL teachers, its results supported impact of occupational self-efficacy, satisfaction and meaning at work in promoting subjective well being in language teachers.

Results of another study conducted by Ilhan, Mete, and Umit (2025) which focused determining the roles played by occupational self-efficacy and resilience as mediators with respect to stress related to one's occupation and teachers level of subjective well- being showed that occupational self-efficacy, resilience had done positive prediction with respect to subjective well- being.

On the other hand, results of another study conducted by Ismayilova and Klassen (2019) to determine research and teaching self-efficacy's relation with job satisfaction among faculties of university faculty showed that job satisfaction and self- efficacy share a positive relation and self-efficacy related to teaching was higher than self-efficacy related to research in university faculty.

It is imperative to build a favorable climate in organization to make teachers jobs more productive, functional, and desirable. Favorable organizational climate includes supportive environment, incentives, praise, detailed information with respect to rules and regulations, encouraging risk taking, promoting autonomy, responsibility and, psychological well-being at workplace (Zahoor, 2011).

Research Questions

- Whether relation exist between communicative competence and occupational self-efficacy in English teachers?
- Whether relation exist between communicative competence and job satisfaction in English teachers?
- Whether relation exist between occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction in English teachers?
- Whether gender differences exist with respect to communicative competence?
- Whether gender differences exist with respect to occupational self-efficacy?
- Whether gender differences exist with respect to job satisfaction?

Objectives of the Study

- Determining relation between communicative competence and occupational self-efficacy in English teachers.
- Determining relation between communicative competence and job satisfaction in English teachers.
- Determining relation between occupational self-efficacy and job satisfaction in English teachers.
- Determining gender differences with respect to communicative competence.
- Determining gender differences with respect to occupational self-efficacy.
- Determining gender differences with respect to job satisfaction.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H1*: Communicative competence shares positive relation with occupational self-efficacy in English teachers.
- *H2*: Communicative competence shares positive relation with job satisfaction in English teachers.
- *H3*: Occupational self-efficacy shares positive relation with job satisfaction in English teachers.
- *H4*: Gender differences exist with respect to communicative competence.
- *H5*: Gender differences exist with respect to occupational self-efficacy.
- *H6*: Gender differences exist with respect to job satisfaction.

Method

Participants

For selecting sample, a non-probability purposive sampling method was used. During the data collection, 50 English teachers were obtained out of which 25 are males and 25 are females.

Figure 1: The above bar graph shows percentage of sample belonging to different genders. The graph shows that 50% of sample are males and 50% of sample are females.

Figure 2: The above bar graph shows percentage of sample belonging to different age groups. the graph shows that 25% of sample are within the age group of 24-29, 35% of sample are within the age group of 30-39, 35% of sample are within the age group of 40-49, and 5% of sample are within the age group of 50-59.

Inclusion Criteria

- Participants within the age group of 24-59 years.
- Participants who are skilled in English.
- Participants who are into English teaching.
- Participants who reside in Kolkata

Exclusion Criteria

- Participants outside the age group of 24- 59 years.
- Participants who are skilled in English.
- Participants who don't teach English.
- Participants who reside outside Kolkata.

Research Design

Correlational design is adopted to determine if there is any relation

between communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction in English teachers . Between group design is adopted for determining gender differences with respect to competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction.

Measures

Communicative Competence: Developed by Weimann (1977) the 36 item Communicative Competence Scale has been used to determine one's ability to share one's thoughts, feelings, and behaviors with other persons and to understand their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. The responses are rated on a five point scale which ranges from *Strongly Agree* (5) to *Strongly Disagree* (1). Item no 4, 8, 11, 12, and 28 are reversed scoring.

Occupational Self-efficacy: Developed by Rigotti et al. (2008) the 6 item Occupational Self-Efficacy Scale has been used to determine one's perception of their abilities in their workplace. The responses are rated on a five point scale which ranges from *Strongly Disagree* (1) to *Strongly Agree* (5).

Job Satisfaction: Developed by Sinval and Marôco (2020) the 5 item Job Satisfaction scale has been used to determine the extent of one's satisfaction with their jobs. The responses are rated on a five point scale which ranges from *Strongly Disagree* (1) to *Strongly Agree* (5).

Procedure

The researcher conducted the study by selecting measures of it and taking permission from participants. This was followed by building up rapport with participants and taking their responses manually. Awareness about confidentiality and voluntary participation was raised by the researcher. Manual responses of the participants have been taken. Then, the information schedule was administered followed by collecting responses and the researcher clearly stated instructions in the questionnaires beforehand. Participants gave responses by taking an average of 10 minutes. The responses were then coded, entered in SPSS, and statistically analysed.

Statistical Analysis:

The responses were scored upon completing data collection. Using, IBM SPSS version 22.0 which is a data analysis software, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was computed to determine the relation between communication competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction in English teachers. t test has been computed to compare gender differences after computing the correlation with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction.

Table 2

Correlation Matrix with Respect to Communicative Competence, Occupational Self-efficacy, and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Communicative Competence	Occupational Self-Efficacy	Job Satisfaction
Communicative Competence	1	0.390**	0.413**
Occupational Self- Efficacy	0.390**	1	0.183
Job Satisfaction	0.413**	0.183	1

Note. p**<0.01 level of significance

Table 2 shows that communicative competence and occupational self-efficacy share a positive relation with each other ($r=.390, p<$

Results and Discussion

Table 1 showing that the mean values of males are 130.12, 22.12, and 18.88 respectively with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. The mean values of females are 132.60, 21.52, and 16.08 respectively with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction.

Table 1 showing that the standard deviation values of males are 23.98, 4.24, 3.94 respectively with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. The standard deviation values of females are 16.34, 6.89, and 3.76 respectively with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction.

Table 1

Mean and Standard Deviation of Males and Females with Respect to Communicative Competence, Occupational Self-efficacy, and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Males (N=25)		Females (N=25)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Communicative Competence	130.12	23.98	132.60	16.34
Occupational Self-efficacy	22.12	4.24	21.52	6.89
Job Satisfaction	18.88	3.94	16.08	3.76

Figure 3: Mean values of males and females with respect to communicative competence, occupational self-efficacy, and job satisfaction can be seen from the bar graph. The bar graph shows that the mean values of males and females with respect to communicative competence are 130.12 and 132.60 respectively. Mean values of males and females with respect to occupational self-efficacy are 22.12 and 21.52 respectively. Mean values of males and females with respect to job satisfaction are 18.88 and 16.08 respectively.

0.01). Thus, the null hypothesis is being rejected and hypothesis H1 is being accepted.

The probable reason behind this result could be traced back to Bandura's social cognitive theory which states that gaining expertise over one's communication skills helps a person to enhance their beliefs in their abilities to perform tasks effectively in their workplaces. In this context, personal mastery plays important role. When a person does effective communication in the workplace like presenting ideas, clearing doubts of others, resolving workplace conflicts which give positive outcomes, it strengthen their abilities to overcome workplace challenges by exerting mastery. That in turn enhances their efficacy levels in the workplace (Nabavi & Bijandi, 2012).

Results of a study conducted by Park et al. (2015) to determine communicative competence, self- efficacy, and job satisfaction's relation in nurses working in the emergency medical center setting of Korea showed a positive relation between communication competence, self- efficacy, and job satisfaction among nurses working in the emergency room (ER).

Table 2 shows that communicative competence and job satisfaction share positive relation with each other ($r=.413, p<0.01$). Thus, the null hypothesis is being rejected and hypothesis H2 is being accepted.

Employees could do certain activities like sharing information, building relationships, absorbing organizational culture and values, and building mutually beneficial relationship with the organization through effective communication (Men & Bowen, 2017). This in turn enhances social relations among members of organization and creates reciprocity towards the organization and job satisfaction in employees and every member of organization (Mehra & Nickerson, 2019).

Results of the study conducted by Madlock (2008) to determine link between leadership style, communicator competence, and employee satisfaction, showed an association between communication, leadership, and job and communication satisfaction in 220 full time working employees of various companies in Midwest. Results of another study conducted by Tabiee et al. (2018) to determine the relation between communication competence and job satisfaction among hospital nursing staff showed a significant positive relation between communication skills and job satisfaction in them.

Table 2 shows that occupational self- efficacy and job satisfaction don't share relation with each other ($r=.183, p>0.05$). Thus, null hypothesis is being accepted and hypothesis H3 is being rejected.

Table 3

t values of Genders of English Teachers with Respect to Communicative Competence, Occupational Self-efficacy, and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Males	Females	t	Sig
	Mean	Mean		
Communication Competence	130.12	132.60	0.427	0.062*
Occupational Self-Efficacy	22.12	21.52	0.371	0.001
Job Satisfaction	18.88	16.08	2.569	0.580*

Note. $p^*<0.05$ level of significance

Table 3 shows that significant gender differences exist with respect to communicative competence ($t= 0.427, p<0.062$). Thus, the null hypothesis is being rejected and hypothesis H4 is being accepted. Mean values show that females scored higher than males

with respect to communicative competence ($132.60>130.12$).

Previous research has shown active functioning of both temporal lobes in females which helps in language and emotional processing. This bilateral processing is absent in males whose left temporal lobe is more predominant during communication. Also secretion of estrogen hormones in females foster verbal and social skills, growth of language centers in females. Conversely, secretion of testosterone in males has been found to share inverse association with verbal and social skills (Burman et al., 2008).

Findings of research conducted by Ozcaliskan and Goldin-Meadow (2010) to determine differences in sex with respect to first appearance of language in gesture showed girls show faster development than boys in many communicative areas using non verbal cues like eye contact, gesture use, gesture imitation, joint attention, and social referencing. Girls tend to show more active listening and verbal fluency than boys while communicating. They tend to acquire language faster, use more vocabulary, and resort to more relation oriented communication than boys (Barel & Tzischinsky, 2018).

Table 3 shows that no significant gender differences exist with respect to occupational self-efficacy ($t= 0.371, p>0.01$). Thus, the null hypothesis is being accepted and hypothesis H5 is being rejected. Mean values shows that males scored higher than females with respect to occupational self-efficacy ($22.12>21.52$).

Table 3 shows that significant gender differences exist with respect to job satisfaction ($t= 2.569, p<0.580$). Thus, the null hypothesis is being rejected and hypothesis H6 is being accepted. Mean values shows that males scored higher than females with respect to job satisfaction ($18.88>16.08$).

Although, results of previous research have shown that females tend to feel satisfied with their jobs more than males but results of this research which showed males feel satisfied with their jobs more than females contradict with results of previous researches (Clark, 1997). Men, we have seen focus more on extrinsic factors like pay and advancement and structural advantages like easier promotions. Women on the other hand tend to focus more on intrinsic factors like relationship and work content (Bokemeier & William, 1987).

Results of another study conducted by Rathod (2023) which focused to determine gender differences in job performance and job satisfaction among government employees showed significant gender differences where males scored higher in job satisfaction than females.

Findings of this quantitative study suggest that soft skills training should be included in school curriculum with special focus on English speaking skills considering scenario of today's world so students don't face any kind of communication barrier and can become confident enough during conversation in their career lives during their adulthood. This would enhance their self- efficacy levels with respect to their occupations and would bring them job satisfaction.

Critical Analysis

Limitation of the study is that it has a very small sample size, focused on a particular place (Kolkata in this case), and applied self reported scales for data collection which might affect generalization of results.

References

- Barel, E., & Tzischinsky, O. (2018). Age and sex differences in verbal and visuospatial abilities. *Advances in Cognitive Psychology*, 2(14), 51.

- Belasoto, M. (2021). Communicative competence of college English language teachers: Using results as basis for an action plan. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 04. 10.47191/ijsshr/v4-i6-47.
- Bokemeier, J. L., & William, B. L. (1987). Job values, rewards, and work conditions as factors in job satisfaction among men and women. *The Sociological Quarterly*, 28(2), 189-204.
- Burman, D. D., Bitan, T., & Booth, J. R. (2008). Sex differences in neural processing of language among children. *Neuropsychologia*, 46(5), 1349-1362.
- Cannale, M. (1983). From communicative competence to communicative language-pedagogy. In J.C. Richards and R. Schmidt (Eds.), *W, Language and Communication*. Longman, London.
- Chamani, S., Safaeizadeh, F., & Xodabande, I. (2023). Investigating the relationship between language teachers' occupational self-efficacy, satisfaction and meaning at work, and their subjective well-being. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1219130.
- Çiçek, I., Sipahioğlu, M., & Dilekçi, Ü. (2025). The mediating role of occupational self-efficacy and resilience in the relationship between occupational stress and subjective well-being in teachers: Validation of the Turkish version of the teacher occupational self-efficacy-short form. *Psychology in the Schools*, 62, 1-16. 10.1002/pits.70073.
- Clark, A. (1997). Job satisfaction and gender: Why are women so happy at work? *Labour Economics*, 4(4), 341-372.
- Çulibrk, J., et al. (2018). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment and job involvement: The mediating role of job involvement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 1132.
- Caena, F., & Redecker, C. (2019). Aligning teacher competence frameworks to 21st century challenges: The case for the European Digital Competence Framework for Educators (Digcompedu). *European Journal of Education*, 54(3), 356-369. doi: 10.1111/ejed.12345.
- Felfe, J., & Schyns, B. (2006). Personality and the perception of transformational leadership: the impact of extraversion, neuroticism, personal need for structure, and occupational self-efficacy. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 36, 708-739. 10.1111/j.0021-9029.2006.00026.x.
- Fradd, S. H., & Lee, O. (1998). Development of a knowledge base for ESOL teacher education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 14(7), 761-773.
- Hymes, D. (1983). Towards ethnographies of communication: The analysis of communicative events. In P.P. Giglioli (Eds.), *Language and social context*. Penguin Book, London.
- Harden, R. M., & Crosby, J. (2000). AMEE guide no 20: The good teacher is more than a lecturer The twelve roles of the teacher. *Medical Teacher*, 22(4), 334-347. doi: 10.1080/014215900409429.
- Ismayilova, K., & Klassen, R. (2019). Research and teaching self-efficacy of university faculty: Relations with job satisfaction. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 98. 10.1016/j.ijer.2019.08.012.
- Madlock, P. (2008). The link between leadership style, communicator competence, and employee satisfaction. *Journal of Business Communication*, 45, 61-78. 10.1177/0021943607309351.
- Mehra, P., & Nickerson, C. (2019). Organizational communication and job satisfaction: What role do generational differences play? *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 27(3), 524-547.
- Men R. L., & Bowen S. A. (2017). *Excellence in internal relations management*. Business Expert Press.
- Özçalışkan, Ş., & Goldin-Meadow, S. (2010). Sex differences in language first appear in gesture. *Developmental Science*, 13(5), 752-760.
- Park, M.G., Blitzer, E.J., Gibbs, J., Losey, J.E., & Danforth, B.N. (2015). Relationships among communication competence, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction in Korean nurses working in the emergency medical center setting. *The Journal of Nursing Research : JNR*, 23. 10.1097/jnr.0000000000000059.
- Rathod, S.S. (2023). Gender differences in job performance and job satisfaction among government employees. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(3), 4895-4899. DIP:18.01.458.20231103, DOI:10.25215/458.
- Rigotti, T., Schyns, B., & Mohr, G. (2008). A short version of the occupational self-efficacy scale: Structural and construct validity across five countries. *Journal of Career Assessment*, 16. 10.1177/1069072707305763.
- Savignon, S. J. (1983). *Communicative competence : Theory and classroom practice*, Ddison-Wesly: Publishing Company, Massachusetts.
- Schneider, B., & Snyder, R. A. (1975). Some relationships between job satisfaction and organization climate. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 60(3), 3-18.
- Sinval, J., & Maroco, J. (2020). Short index of job satisfaction: Validity evidence from Portugal and Brazil. *PLOS ONE*, 15, 1-21. 10.1371/journal.pone.0231474.
- Tabiee, S., Sharifzadeh, G., & Saeedi, E. (2018). The relationship of communication skills with job satisfaction among hospital nursing staff. *Modern Care Journal*. In Press. 10.5812/modernc.81590.
- Tadayon, N.R., & Bijandi, M. (2012). Bandura's social learning theory and social cognitive learning theory. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 1, 589.
- Tarone, E. (1985). A closer look at some inter language terminology: A framework for communicative strategies. In C. Fearch and G. Kasper (Eds.), *Strategies in interlanguage communication*. Longman, London.
- Usman, B., Silviyanti, T. M., & Marzatillah, M. (2016). The influence of teacher's competence towards the motivation of students in learning English. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 3(2), 134-146.
- Wallin, S., Rauhala, A., Fjellman-Wiklund, A., Nyman, P., & Fagerström, L. (2021). Occupational self-efficacy and work engagement associated with work ability among an ageing work force: A cross-sectional study. *Work*, 70(2), 591-602. Doi: 10.3233/WOR-213595. PMID: 34657840.
- Wiemann, J. M. (1977). Explication and test of a model of communicative competence. *Human Communication Research*, 3, 195-213.
- Zahoor, Z. (2011). *Influence of organizational climate, teaching attitude, and adjustment on job satisfaction of teachers*. Unpublished doctoral Dissertation, Department of Psychology, Aligarh Muslim University: India.

Received December 2, 2025

Revision received January 29, 2026

Accepted February 5, 2026